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DEVELOPMENT OF A SYSTEM WITH A CUMULATIVE TEMPERATURE NOTIFICATION FUNCTION FOR SOIL SOLARIZATION

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In Okinawa, Japan, marine pollution caused by red soil runoff has become a serious and long-term environmental problem. To mitigate this issue, ground cover plants such as Kurapia (improved *Lippia nodiflora*) have been introduced to stabilize the soil surface. However, in some areas, their growth remains limited due to poor soil structure and fertility. For such soil conditions, soil solarization based on the BLOF theory can be highly effective. This method utilizes solar radiation to increase cumulative soil temperature, suppress harmful pathogens, and improve soil aggregation in an environmentally friendly manner. This study aims to develop an automated monitoring and notification system to efficiently manage the soil solarization process. The proposed system measures multiple environmental parameters and issues alerts when the cumulative temperature reaches a specified threshold. A web-based application built using FastAPI enables real-time visualization of temperature changes and cumulative temperature trends. The system is based on a Raspberry Pi Model B and uses DS18B20 and DHT22 sensors to measure soil temperature, ambient humidity, and CPU temperature. When the threshold value of 90°C proposed in the BLOF theory is exceeded, the system automatically sends notifications to users via Gmail. Field experiments were conducted outdoors using a mobile battery and router to evaluate long-term data acquisition performance under different conditions. The results showed stable operation at night, while significant increases in internal and CPU temperatures were observed during the day. These findings indicate that improving ventilation and thermal insulation are essential for stable operation under high-temperature conditions. Future work will focus on integrating a solar power module to achieve complete energy autonomy and incorporating machine learning algorithms to predict cumulative temperature trends and estimate the curing completion time. This system aims to contribute to sustainable agricultural practices by providing a low-cost, data-driven solution for soil health management.

Keywords: Soil solarization, Raspberry Pi, Soil monitoring, BLOF theory

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